

Do Surgeons Forget? Investigating the Impact of Days out of Practice on Health Outcomes for Emergency Hip Fracture Patients

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Learning-by-doing is a major aspect of surgeons' training. An important potential determinant of learning is frequency of practice, empirically measured by the number of days between two surgeries. Causal evidence on the importance of surgical skill maintenance on patient outcomes is however scarce.

This study's objective is to understand how the time elapsed between surgeries affects a surgeon's performance in the context of hip fracture surgery. Despite the high incidence (around 75,000 hip fractures occur annually in the UK), hip fracture care is complex and mortality remains high, at around 7 percent at one month after surgery.

Data & Methods: The dataset comprises detailed patient-level hospital administrative data for all emergency hip fracture patients admitted in England between 2008 and 2016, corresponding to an unbalanced panel dataset of over 2,000 orthopaedic surgeons. Post-surgery health outcomes are measured using patients' 30-day mortality rate.

Using a fixed effects model, I explore whether the number of days elapsed between two hip fracture cases have an impact on a surgeon's outcomes, controlling for a rich set of patients' clinical and socio-economic factors (e.g. age, gender, ethnicity, comorbidities, socio-economic deprivation, day of the week dummies for admission or pre-surgery length of stay). Surgeon fixed effects account for unobserved heterogeneity in surgeon quality. Interacted hospital-year dummies further control for potential confounders linked to hospital-specific changes in operating theatres, medical equipment or hospital heterogeneity in adaptation of national clinical guidelines over time.

Individuals who are more able at a task may increase their rate of practice of such task, thus creating an endogeneity bias in estimates of practice frequency of surgical ability. These are addressed by testing the potential for surgeons' forgetting in the context of emergency hip fractures. Patients break their proximal femur, often following a fall, and need to be treated within 48 hours of admission to the closest hospital. This creates a plausibly exogenous variation in surgeons' time breaks, conditional on surgeon fixed effects and the set of controls.

Results: Results show that time interruptions in practice do not have a causal negative effect on health outcomes. These results are robust to additionally controlling for the time elapsed since any surgical activity and surgeons' seniority.

I however find that average patients' health outcomes improve with breaks of between 15 and 30 days, as the probability of 30-day mortality reduces by 0.4 percentage points (7 percent relative effect) compared to surgeons who performed a hip fracture surgery the day before.

I further investigate potential causal channels and show that these positive effects are not mediated by differences in treatment choice or longer post-surgical length of stay. This suggests a detrimental effect of surgical fatigue with higher frequency of practice and is consistent with evidence on the detrimental effect of long work shifts on surgical performance.